

Optimizing Student Internship Management with a Website System Based on Latest Technology at Politeknik Nest

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Abstract:

The Student Internship Program is a mandatory course for all Diploma-3 students at Politeknik Nest Sukoharjo. The information required by students and lecturers regarding the Student Internship Program is extensive, and the service is not yet computerized. The purpose of this research is to develop an information system by designing and building a website for recording student internships at Politeknik Nest Sukoharjo. In accordance with the research objectives, this study employs methods such as observation, interviews, document analysis, and literature review. The case study for this research is the Development of a Student Internship Recording Website for Politeknik Nest Sukoharjo. The Student Internship Information System serves as a tool to assist institutions, students, and lecturers in the student internship process. This system is developed as a web-based application using a MySQL database and PHP programming language. MySQL is an open-source and free database management system (DBMS) software. It is used to access, modify, and manipulate data on a relational scale. PHP, short for Hypertext Preprocessor, is an open-source programming language used to build dynamic and interactive web applications.

Keywords: *Information System, MySQL, PHP, Student Internship, Website*

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Introduction

Internship is an activity designed for students to apply their knowledge and gain real-world work experience. An internship program can also be implemented to enhance the reputation of an educational institution (Nugraheni & Sinatra Wijaya, 2017). The internship program not only enhances students' personal skills but also refines their professional growth and experience (Anjum, 2020). Internship is a form of systematic and synchronized implementation between educational programs at schools or universities and skill mastery programs gained through direct work activities in the professional world to achieve a certain level of expertise (Lestari & Novita, 2019). Internship and independent study programs greatly help in enhancing students' competencies, both in hard skills and soft skills. These programs also provide students with the opportunity for experiential learning in workplaces or industries, serving as valuable preparation for entering the professional world after graduating from university (Arisandi et al., 2022). Internships provide young people with the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the industry and gain relevant experience (Francis & Alagas, 2017). Incorporating industrial internship programs into the curriculum has become a crucial requirement to ensure a holistic education system. Providing students with opportunities to gain real-world work experience is essential as a strategy to enhance their employability after graduation (Karunaratne & Perera, 2019).

Students play a vital role in an organization or institution, as they are both subjects and objects in the process of applying knowledge and skills. To enhance activities related to providing internship opportunities, fast and accurate administration for internship registration is essential. One of the challenges in internship programs is that attendance reporting and daily activity documentation are still not well-organized and are conducted in a conventional manner (Yulianto & Firdaus, 2021). The administration of internship activities should facilitate interns in completing the registration process and reporting their internship activities.

The internship registration process at Politeknik NEST is currently done manually, which has the disadvantage that prospective interns must complete the paperwork manually. After the internship period ends, interns are required to submit an internship report. There are two issues with the current internship program: the internship activities are not properly recorded, and there is no system in place to manage the activities of the interns.

Based on the description above, the objective of this research is to optimize internship management by developing a website-based information system that can manage internship activities, including registration, letter issuance, daily journals, final internship reports, and seminar invitations. This system aims to replace the old conventional system with a more computerized one that can process and manage internship activity information more quickly, accurately, and centrally. The use of website-based technology facilitates the delivery of information to users in an easy and fast manner, with the ability to connect via the internet (Hariyanto, 2021).

Related Work

The research conducted by (Lestari & Novita, 2019) state that the internship process requires a registration method that is not brief. It begins with the need to visit the office or company in person to inquire about available internship vacancies, followed by submitting a proposal along with a cover letter. The proposal then needs to be processed, which may take several days, or even more than a week, until it is approved by the authorities. As a result, students must constantly follow up to track the progress of their application.

The research conducted by (Hasti et al., 2019) state that the internship information system can assist the treasurer in managing internship payments and printing transaction receipts, help the program coordinator in processing internship applications, determine the companies where students will undertake internships, assign mentors, and print internship application letters. It also helps in data collection for reports, assists mentors in managing grades, and enables students to easily access internship information. With integrated data, it simplifies the process of creating reports.

The research conducted by (Yulianto & Firdaus, 2021) designed an information system to replace the conventional system of attendance and daily activity reporting for internship students, transitioning to a computerized system so that the entire process and information management can run smoothly and centrally.

The research conducted by (Hariyanto, 2021) states that the use of technology developed through a website can facilitate the process of delivering information to users in an easy and fast manner, with the ability to connect via the internet. Due to its ease of operation and flexible nature, the web-based internship information system application is developed to simplify internship recruitment and provide relevant information about the internship process.

The research conducted by (Pratama et al., 2022) developed an information system to facilitate the internship process. The system that is built will be mapped, created, designed, and programmed into a website to execute the internship process flow. It uses programming languages and frameworks such as HTML, CSS, and PHP for the backend process.

The research conducted by (Rindiani et al., 2023) developed an internship acceptance information system to simplify the internship application process for students and to improve efficiency and effectiveness in accepting internship students. This system offers important features, including online registration, file submission, and status tracking. Students can fill out the online registration form and upload documents such as CVs, transcripts, and other recommendation letters.

Research Method

The data collection methods used are field studies and literature reviews. The field study involves observation, interviews, and document analysis.

Observation: Data is collected by reviewing the official website of the Siakad Politeknik NEST (<https://nest.ecampuz.com/>) and examining related journals and research to determine the functional requirements of the application.

Interviews: The purpose of data collection is to gather further information about internship documentation from the academic division of Politeknik NEST Sukoharjo. The interview aims to determine whether the relevant parties require an Internship Recording Mechanism.

Document Analysis: Collecting and studying documents related to the development of the application is the method used for document analysis.

Literature Review: To conduct this research, the sources of information used are websites, scientific journals, and other readings.

The application development method uses the waterfall model in system development. It starts with analysis, design, implementation, integration, and testing.

Analysis: This phase must address all software requirements, including the expected functionality and software constraints. To obtain this information, interviews, surveys, or discussions are typically conducted. The data is then analyzed to create user requirement documentation for use in the next phase.

Design: Before coding, this phase aims to provide an overview of what the system should do and how it should look. It also helps determine hardware and system requirements, as well as defining the overall system architecture.

Implementation: In this phase, programming is carried out, meaning the creation of the computer program is divided into smaller modules that will be integrated in the next phase. Additionally, the created modules are tested to ensure they perform the desired functions.

Integration and Testing: At this point, the created modules are integrated and tested to ensure that the software matches the design and is free of errors.

Figure 1 shows the flowchart of the application development for the research, explaining the process of implementing the internship management information system at Politeknik NEST.

Figure 1. Research application development flowchart

Problem Identification: The problem identification process includes identifying and evaluating issues that arise during the development of the internship management information system. This phase also involves determining the research subjects.

Literature Review: The literature review collects information from previous studies as reference data for the current research.

Data Collection: In this phase, observation, interviews, and document collection are used to gather data on internship participants at Politeknik NEST and other necessary data for the research.

System Analysis: System analysis begins by reviewing the current system and determining what is needed for the internship management information system. This phase also provides an overview of the advantages and disadvantages of the developed system.

System Design: Designing user flows for the application, database design, IT infrastructure design, and user interface design for the built application are all part of the system design phase.

Coding: Coding is the phase where the system design is implemented. During this phase, the program code for the application is written, and a web-based application is developed.

System Testing: The system testing process includes building the system environment, installing supporting components, and testing the developed application. This phase produces data on the quality of the application.

Report: The report phase involves documenting the analysis, design, and testing of the developed system. The report provides research analysis and serves as a reference for future research.

Result and Discussion

The system design is illustrated using a use case diagram to depict the functionalities within the developed information system.

Figure 2. Use Case Diagram

Based on Figure 2, the Use Case Diagram above shows that there are two actors: the admin, managed by each head of the study program, and the students, each of whom has their own account. The admin can check the registrants' data, review the uploaded documents, and validate whether the documents uploaded by students are correct or need revisions, input internship grades, and seminar grades. Meanwhile, students can register, download document formats, upload documents, and submit seminar applications. Below is the display of the internship information system page.

Figure 3. Login Page

Login using NIM and PASSWORD. The password is obtained from each student's academic advisor.

Figure 4. Dashboard page to complete the registrant's data

After a successful login, students will be directed to the Dashboard page, which contains the student's identity and the industry where the internship will take place. Once the data is complete, an indicator will appear to confirm that the data is complete.

Figure 5. Download registration letter page

Once the data is complete, the next step is for students to download the Registration Form available in the Document Format menu. Check the data accuracy before proceeding with the download. If the data is correct, click the print letter button. If the data is incomplete, the "Incomplete" indicator will not be green. If the data is incomplete, the print letter button cannot be clicked. Once the letter is printed, sign it. Then, the student must request approval and the letter number from their respective head of study program.

POLITEKNIK NEST FORMULIR PENDAFTARAN PROGRAM MAGANG	
PILIHAN PROGRAM	<input type="checkbox"/> LUAR NEGERI <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DALAM NEGERI <input type="checkbox"/> KEWIRAUSAHAAN
NEGARAKOTA PILIHAN	Surabaya
NAMA MITRA IDUKA	PT. Teman Inovasi Digital
ALAMAT IDUKA	Solo Technopark, Gedung Solo Trade Center II, Ki Hajar Dewantara, Karanggeni, Kota Surakarta, Jawa Tengah 57139
PERIODE	12 Maret 2023 - 6 Juli 2023
NAMA DEPARTEMEN	Developer Webapp
DATA MAHASISWA	
NAMA MAHASISWA	LESTERA BRUMI
NIM/SEMESTER	35130464 / 4
TAHUN ANGIKATAN	2023
NO. HP AKTIF	08962603472
ALAMAT RUMAH	Badrulbari RT 08 RW 08, Papan, Tasikmalda, Karanganyar
ALAMAT EMAIL	hassanmuhre@gmail.com
PERSETUJUAN	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> LESTERA BRUMI TTD MAHASISWA </div> </div>
No.Surat : IIV/23/PPTS-2 NOMOR SURAT	

SURAT PERNYATAAN PROGRAM MAGANG - POLITEKNIK NEST	
Bersama ini, saya yang bertandatangan:	
Nama : LESTERA BRUMI NIM : 35130464 Alamat Rumah : Badrulbari RT 08 RW 08, Papan, Tasikmalda, Karanganyar	
Menyatakan bahwa saya bersedia mengikuti program ini dengan mengikuti prosedur dan peraturan yang ada dengan mengabdikan semua dengan kesungguhan yang ada.	
Demikian Surat Pernyataan ini saya buat dengan sebenar-benarnya.	
TTD ORANGTUA MAHASISWA (Nama: [Redacted])	

Figure 6. Example of the downloaded letter

Figure 7. Registration form upload page

After the Registration Form is complete, the next step is to upload the form into the system through the Upload Documents menu → Registration Form. Before uploading, make sure the file requirements meet the necessary criteria. Once verified as correct and complete, click the Upload Document button and select the document.

Figure 8. Display for selecting the document to be uploaded

After selecting the document, click the upload button. If the document is successfully uploaded, a notification will appear confirming that the document has been uploaded successfully.

Figure 9. Document upload successful display

The student then downloads all the recommended documents, such as the CV document for internship registration, the internship journal document for recording and reporting daily activities at the internship site, the internship report document for creating the internship report before the internship process is completed (at least one month before the internship ends, the report should start being created), the internship assessment document for evaluating the internship

site, the seminar invitation document for the internship seminar invitation once all internship reports are completed and approved by the internship supervisor, and the seminar evaluation document for grading the internship seminar presentation.

Result

A web-based information system for managing internship participants at Politeknik Nest Sukoharjo has been successfully developed, using PHP programming language, HTML framework, and MySQL database.

Discussion

This application is built to make it easier for users to manage internship participants. For the application to run more optimally, further development is needed in line with user needs and future functionalities. There are still limitations/shortcomings in the application that has been created. Some functionalities or developments that can be added in future development include: Development of the application for mobile platforms, Addition of notification features between the person in charge and internship participants, Addition of an attendance feature for internship participants.

Conclusion

The design and development of the internship participant management information system for the study program at Politeknik Nest has been successfully carried out. The system development method used in the development of this application adopts the stages of the waterfall model system development, which include data collection and analysis, design, implementation, and system testing. Data and information related to the research were collected and analyzed, resulting in several functional requirements for the proposed system, which consists of 2 actors: admin and internship participants. This application is built on a web platform using PHP programming language and MySQL database.

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